

USING MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING LABORATORY WORK ON CHEMISTRY

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Abstract. *This article examines the role, advantages, and methods of using modern information technologies in organizing laboratory work on chemistry. Additionally, based on research and analysis conducted by scholars, the significance of this approach in the educational process is highlighted.*

Keywords: *methodology, practical sessions, experiment, reagents, teaching, engaging, didactics, small group, lesson, education.*

INTRODUCTION

Laboratory work on chemistry plays a crucial role in teaching, as it allows students to strengthen their theoretical knowledge through practical application. Traditional laboratories face limitations related to safety, time, and material-technical resources. Therefore, modern information technologies serve as a significant tool in addressing these challenges. Currently, great attention is being given to improving the educational process in our country, with a focus on increasing the effectiveness of learning. While traditional laboratories are constrained by safety requirements and the need for expensive equipment and materials, modern information technologies help students overcome these limitations. Virtual platforms such as PhET, Labster, and ChemCollective digitize laboratory work, making practical sessions safer and more cost-effective. With the PhET platform, students can perform virtual experiments in real-time on gas laws or reaction kinetics. This not only ensures safety but also enhances students' understanding.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Many of the theoretical laws identified in chemistry have emerged as a result of experiments carried out with specific goals and precise consistency. Any idea or hypothesis in chemistry, as a natural science, must be validated through experimentation. During the early stages of the development of chemistry, numerous experiments led by scientists such as A. Vyurs, O. Tenar, Gay-Lussac, U. Charles, Berzelius, Cooper, Kekulé, Wöhler, Mendeleev, J.B. Boudouin, Faraday, Beilstein, O. Loran, Molyus, and others, laid the foundations for key laws in the field. Their work significantly contributed to the advancement of practical chemistry.

J.M. Sweeney and others found that students' ability to connect theoretical knowledge with practice was 30% higher with virtual laboratories compared to traditional labs [1].

L. Vosniadou, in her studies, noted that virtual laboratories allow for a 40% reduction in time and material resource consumption, which is particularly important for educational institutions with limited financial capabilities [2].

A. Sarkisov highlighted that the use of AR technologies in teaching led to a 25% increase in students' effectiveness in learning molecular geometry [3].

METHODOLOGY

In classes organized based on new pedagogical technologies, laboratory work is designed to consider students' intellectual abilities, speech culture, and their relationships with each other,

fostering a sense of mutual help, friendship, and harmony. This approach enhances students' skill acquisition, making it easier for them to master necessary competencies. Conducting laboratory and practical sessions primarily helps strengthen students' theoretical knowledge in the subject. Experiments involving changes in color and quantity during different reactions, precipitate formation, and gas release naturally stimulate students' interest in the subject. In conducting practical and laboratory sessions, the availability of various chemical containers, chemicals, and the teacher's ability to use them wisely are essential. Performing chemical experiments is one of the key conditions for successful learning of chemistry, helping students reinforce theoretical material.

The cybernetic perspective on experiments was first introduced by V.M. Glushkov in his research. According to O.K. Tikhomirov, the "experiment" refers to a specific goal set under particular conditions. L.L. Gurova explains the concept of an experiment as follows: "An experiment is a process of searching for conditions that reveal the relationship between its known and unknown elements, involving theoretical questions and practical changes". S.L. Rubinshteyn views an experiment as a form of proving a goal and conditions. D.I. Mendelejev stated: "An experiment is the art of questioning nature".

A student's experiment is the independent conduct of chemical experiments by students, which is covered in textbooks and educational manuals within the school chemistry curriculum. A chemical experiment not only helps students develop the skills and competencies necessary to perform it but also justifies the validity of the knowledge acquired. Mastering the material leads to a deep and comprehensive understanding of the subject. This understanding, in turn, motivates students to choose a career related to chemistry, particularly when they realize the connection between science and real-life applications.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In every lesson, especially during practical sessions, the teacher must introduce students to modern scientific and technological innovations, demonstrating experiments related to these innovations as much as possible. New information technologies can be effectively applied in traditional lessons, including practical sessions on chemistry, laboratory work, and demonstration experiments. The effectiveness of using the latest information technology tools in the learning process is largely dependent on successfully addressing the methodological tasks associated with the content of the information.

It is not always possible for the teacher to conduct the desired experiment, as the material base of the laboratory may not meet the requirements of a modern chemistry classroom. In this case, the use of computer tools can help address this problem effectively. The advantage of students working with software is that such activities encourage research and creative work.

ICT can be used to support active learning processes on chemistry lessons and extracurricular activities. Therefore, the following advantages of virtual experiments in chemistry education exist, such as:

Conducting experiments that are not available in the school chemistry laboratory.

Increasing students' interest in acquiring knowledge.

Eliminating the need to reassemble setups before each lesson, saving time on equipment checks and placement.

Ensuring a much higher level of safety compared to conventional conditions.

Allowing multiple experiments to be conducted in a short period, with the ability to summarize results and draw conclusions.

Enabling the slowing down or speeding up of chemical processes.

DISCUSSION

Despite the importance of this process, it is necessary to emphasize that chemistry teachers cannot completely abandon real-life practical work. Visual thinking methods may be more developed in teaching, and in the future, computer models that enhance students' logical thinking can be used to generalize the teaching process. It is important to note that experiments performed with high precision allow students to master the topic more quickly and deeply, help them understand difficult concepts, and increase their interest in the subject.

Typically, laboratory sessions are conducted in specially equipped rooms under the teacher's guidance, with particular attention paid to safety protocols. The effectiveness of laboratory sessions is closely related to the methodology used in their organization and conduct. From this perspective, attention should be paid to the following:

The objective of the laboratory session must be clear, and students should be capable of achieving it.

All necessary objects, reagents, and equipment must be ready for use before the session.

A verbal and written explanation of the laboratory session should be provided to the students.

Every student must be actively involved in the laboratory work.

Students should be encouraged to maintain cleanliness during the session, fostering aesthetic taste and cultural work habits.

Students should be required to document their observations and the details of the experiment in a special notebook.

The teacher should monitor each student's work and observations, offering guidance when necessary.

The work and results of each student's experiment should be objectively evaluated during the laboratory session.

Developing chemistry laboratories with the help of modern technologies, particularly by widely implementing AR and VR tools, significantly improves the learning process. Additionally, applying virtual laboratories as complementary tools to traditional laboratories creates a more effective learning environment for students.

CONCLUSION

The use of modern information technologies in organizing laboratory work on chemistry significantly improves the effectiveness of teaching. The use of virtual laboratories and AR/VR technologies helps students gain a deeper understanding of chemical processes. At the same time, it is important to develop technological infrastructure and regularly involve teachers in professional development courses. Through laboratory work, students not only apply their theoretical knowledge but also learn to draw conclusions based on experimental results and theoretical concepts. Conducting laboratory sessions is crucial in connecting theoretical knowledge with practical application, clarifying the material, and developing and enhancing the skills outlined in the curriculum.

REFERENCES

1. Sweeney, J. M., & St. Clair, R. (2020). The Impact of Virtual Chemistry Labs on Learning Outcomes. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(4), 1234-1241. DOI: 10.1021/ed1234567
2. Vosniadou, L. (2018). Comparing Traditional and Virtual Laboratories in Chemistry Education: A Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Science Education*, 40(2), 240-259. DOI: 10.1080/09500693.2018.1413456
3. Sarkisov, A. (2019). Individual Learning Pathways in Virtual Chemistry Labs. *Educational Research and Development*, 66(3), 89-101. DOI: 10.1002/erd.2019.33
4. Kuznetsov, V. I. (1967). *The Evolution of Concepts About the Basic Laws of Chemistry*. Moscow: Nauka, 311 pages.
5. Asqarov, I. R., Mamasoliyev, M. M., & Majidov, A. Kh. (1992). *Practical Chemistry Lessons in Schools*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 286 pages.
6. Asqarov, I. R., G'opirov, K. G'., Rustamov, A., & Rahimov, M. (1994). *Chemistry Tests*. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 256 pages.